

Application of generalized linear models in big data: a divide and recombine (D&R) approach

Md. Mahadi Hassan Nayem Nayem^{1*}
and Dr. Soma Chowdhury Biswas Biswas¹

^{1*}Department of Statistics, University of Chittagong, Hathazari,
Chattogram, 4331, Bangladesh.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): mhnayem.cu.stat@outlook.com;
Contributing authors: soma.stat@cu.ac.bd;

Abstract

D&R is a statistical approach designed to handle large and complex datasets. It partitions the dataset into several manageable subsets and subsequently applies the analytic method to each subset independently to obtain results. Finally, the results from each subset are combined to yield the results for the entire dataset. D&R strategies can be implemented to fit GLMs to datasets too large for conventional methods. Several D&R strategies are available for different GLMs, some of which are theoretically justified but lack practical validation. A significant limitation is the theoretical and practical justification for estimating combined standard errors and confidence intervals. This paper reviews D&R strategies for GLMs and proposes a method to determine the combined standard error and confidence interval for D&R-based estimators. In addition to the traditional dataset division procedures, we propose a different division method named sequential partitioning for D&R-based estimators on GLMs. We show that the obtained D&R estimator with the proposed standard error and confidence interval attains equivalent efficiency as the full data estimate. We illustrate this on a large synthetic dataset and verify that the results from D&R are accurate and identical to those from other available R packages.

Keywords: big data, divide and combine, GLMs, synthetic dataset, sequential partitioning

1 Introduction

Generalized linear models (GLMs) form a general framework for modeling the relationship between a response and a set of predictors. It was first introduced by [Nelder and Wedderburn \(1972\)](#) to provide a unifying set of models widely used for regression analysis. GLM is a flexible extension of ordinary OLS that enables the linear model to be related to response through a link function. Standard statistical modeling, such as GLMs, is based on a single dataset that may be very large and becomes unwieldy to work with from a computational perspective. The divide and recombine (D&R) approach was developed to overcome these limitations in response to recent trends in data science and big data research.

The Divide and Recombine technique has proven to be an effective and generic approach to the statistical analysis of large-scale datasets([Guha et al., 2012](#)). It partitions the data into manageable subsets, applies analytical methods to each subset, and subsequently aggregates the result. The computations are embarrassingly parallel, meaning they can run in parallel without any communication, thus facilitating efficient big-data analysis. Division in datasets can be achieved through either replicate division or conditioning variable division [Bühlmann et al. \(2016\)](#). As per [Cleveland and Hafen \(2014\)](#) and [Hafen \(2016\)](#), replicate division uses random sampling without replacement, whereas conditioning-variable division stratifies data based on one or more variables. The replicate division enables simple and faster computations, but there may be a small loss in accuracy compared to the complete data estimate. The divisions from the dataset should be sufficiently small to be memory-manageable and amenable to further breakdown if needed.

Various compression and aggregation schemes for data cubes in linear and logistic regression models have been proposed, and their efficacy has been demonstrated. Different D&R schemes for Poisson and multinomial models have been suggested, but their practical justification still needs to be verified. Notably, procedures for variance or standard error estimation for D&R-based estimators for GLMs currently need to be made available. This study aims to review D&R schemes for GLMs and proposes an aggregated standard error and confidence interval estimation scheme. The application of the D&R strategy is demonstrated on a synthetic dataset to verify its efficiency with other standard results.

2 D&R for GLMs

This section provides a basic overview of different D&R approaches for GLMs. We focus on four specific generalized linear models (GLMs): linear regression, which is used for continuous response variables; logistic regression, for binary response variables; Poisson regression, for count data; and multinomial logistic regression, which is used for categorical response variables with more than two levels.

2.1 Multiple linear regression model

For extremely large datasets to fit into memory, two practical D&R approaches have been proposed: summary statistics D&R and horizontal D&R. Summary D&R extracts

relevant summary statistics that best summarize data in each subset, ensuring the aggregated estimate is as close to full data estimates as possible. Lee et al. (2017) extracted only summary data, rendering unit record data unnecessary. They proposed the procedure for the following model:

$$Y = X\beta + \epsilon, \quad \epsilon \sim N(0, \Sigma)$$

With the following identity link function:

$$\theta = g(\mu) = \mu = E(Y) = X\beta$$

The least square estimator or ML estimator can be obtained as:

$$\hat{\beta} = (X'X)^{-1} X'Y$$

The summary statistics D&R are illustrated in the following steps:

1. The entire dataset is divided into s subsets, each with a similar structure, where X_s and Y_s are the vectors of the design matrix and the responses to the subset s .
2. Compute $X_s'X_s$ and $X_s'Y_s$, $S = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$.
3. Recombine separate estimates using $\left(\sum_{s=1}^S X_s'X_s\right)^{-1} \left(\sum_{s=1}^S X_s'Y_s\right)$

2.2 Logistic regression model

Let us consider a binary response variable y and the vector of covariates X . Then, the logit function is defined as:

$$\ln\left(\frac{p_i}{1-p_i}\right) = x_i\beta$$

The estimation equation can be obtained as:

$$\frac{\delta l}{\delta \beta_j} = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - p_i] x_{ij} = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, s$$

$$\frac{\delta l}{\delta \beta_j} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[y_i - \frac{e^{x_i\beta}}{1 + e^{x_i\beta}} \right] x_{ij} = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, s$$

where l is defined as a log-likelihood function. Now,

$$\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \beta_j \delta \beta_k} = \frac{\delta}{\delta \beta_k} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - p_i] x_{ij} \right)$$

$$H = \frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \beta_j \delta \beta_k} = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i (1 - p_i) x_{ij} x_{ik}$$

Here, H is the Hessian matrix that represents the second-order partial derivatives of the log-likelihood function with respect to parameters β_j and β_k .

Xi et al. (2008) presented a compression scheme to enable high-quality aggregation of logistic regression in multidimensional data space. They retained only the model parameters and a few auxiliary measures to compress each data segment. A logistic model was constructed via an aggregation formula. The data compression method must fulfill the following criteria:

1. The compressed data in a multidimensional data cube environment should satisfy lossless or asymptotically lossless aggregation of the regression measures.
2. ii. As there may be many tuples in each cell, the complexity in compressed data due to space should be minimal and unaffected by the number of tuples in each cell Xi et al. (2008).

The following steps are used to obtain an aggregated estimator via the D&R technique:

1. The entire dataset is divided into s subsets, each with a similar structure, where $s = 1, 2, 3, \dots, S$. Y_s and X_s are vectors of responses and the design matrix.
2. For the sth subset, compute the Hessian matrix:

$$H_s = \frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \beta_j \delta \beta_k}$$

and $\hat{\beta}_s$ for each subset s from the following equation:

$$l'_s(\beta) = \frac{\delta l_s}{\delta \beta} = \sum_{i=1}^n \{(y_{si} - p_{si}) x_{si}\} = 0$$

3. Aggregate the $\hat{\beta}'_s$ that is obtained in step 2 via the following:

$$\hat{\beta} = \left(\sum_{s=1}^S H_s \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_{s=1}^S H_s \hat{\beta}_s \right)$$

2.3 Poisson regression model

Let us consider an observed count-dependent variable Y , which is assumed to follow a Poisson distribution. λ is called the rate parameter, which is determined by a set of k predictors $X = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k)$. Then, the expression relating to these quantities is:

$$E(Y = y | X) = \lambda = \exp(X\beta)$$

where $X\beta$ is the systematic component and where $\exp(X\beta)$ ensures that λ is positive. Therefore, the Poisson regression model for i observations can be expressed as:

$$P(Y_i = y_i | X_i, \beta) = \frac{e^{-\exp(X\beta)} \exp(X\beta)^{y_i}}{y_i!}$$

That is, the outcome variable follow a Poisson distribution for a given set of predictors with rate $\exp(X\beta)$. For a sample of size n , the likelihood function for the Poisson regression model is given by:

$$L(\beta; y, X) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{e^{-\exp(X\beta)} \exp(X_i\beta)^{y_i}}{y_i!}$$

The log-likelihood function can be expressed as:

$$l(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n [X_i\beta - \exp(X\beta) - \log(y_i!)]$$

The maximization of the log-likelihood function has no close approximation. Here, techniques such as iterative weighted least squares can be implemented to estimate the regression coefficient $\hat{\beta}$. The D&R approach for poison regression described by [Karim et al. \(2019\)](#) is illustrated in the following steps:

1. The entire dataset is divided into s subsets, each with a similar structure, where Y_s and X_s are vectors of responses and the design matrix for subset s .
2. For the sth partitioned subset, compute $\hat{\beta}_s, s = 1, 2, 3, \dots, S$ by solving the following log-likelihood function $l(\beta)$ iteratively:

$$l(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n [X_{si}\beta - \exp(X_{si}\beta) - \log(y_{si}!)]$$

3. 3. Recombine separate estimates obtained from step 2 as:

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{\sum_{s=1}^S \hat{\beta}_s}{S}$$

2.4 Multinomial logistic regression model

In the simple logistic regression model, the response variable is a dichotomous variable taking values of 1 and 0 denoting success and failure as two categories. In practice, a situation arises where Y can ask to address polytomous responses, that is, $r > 2$ categories. When $r = 2$, Y is a dichotomous variable, we model the log odds that an event occurs. When $r = 2$, for a simple logistic regression model, we can form a logit function as follows: $logit(p) = \log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$

When we deal with multi-category or polytomous response variables, i.e., $r > 2$, $\frac{r(r-1)}{2}$ logits (odds), but only $(r - 1)$ are nonredundant. These $(r - 1)$ nonredundant logits can be formed in different ways, leading to different polytomous (multinomial) logistic regression models. Let the outcome variable Y possess r categories $Y_1 = y_1, \dots, Y_r = y_r$, where $\sum_{j=1}^r y_j = n$. The probability mass function of Y_1, \dots, Y_r is said to follow a multinomial distribution with probabilities

$P(Y_1 = y_1) = p_1, P(Y_2 = y_2) = p_2, \dots, P(Y_r = y_r) = p_r$ as:

$$P \left[Y_1 = y_1, Y_2 = y_2, \dots, Y_r = y_r \left| \sum_{j=1}^r y_j = n \right. \right] = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^r \frac{e^{-\lambda_j} \lambda_j^{y_j}}{y_j!}}{\frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^n}{n!}} = n! \prod_{j=1}^r \frac{\left(\frac{\lambda_j}{\lambda}\right)^{y_j}}{y_j!}$$

which is equivalent to the multinomial form with $p_j = \frac{\lambda_j}{\lambda}$. The expression stated above can be expressed in exponential form as:

$$P \left[Y_1 = y_1, Y_2 = y_2, \dots, Y_r = y_r \left| \sum_{j=1}^r y_j = n \right. \right] = e^{(\sum_{j=1}^r y_j \ln\left(\frac{\lambda_j}{\lambda}\right) + \ln(n!) - \ln(\sum_{j=1}^r y_j!))}$$

For Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_r , the link function is given by:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\lambda_{ij}}{\lambda_{i1}}\right) = x_{ij}\beta_j, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n.$$

where, $x_{ij} = (1, x_{ij1}, x_{ij2}, \dots, x_{ijp})$ and $\beta_j = (\beta_{j0}, \beta_{j1}, \dots, \beta_{jp})'$. Now, the log-likelihood function is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} l &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^r \left[y_{ij} \ln\left(\frac{\lambda_{ij}}{\lambda_i}\right) + \ln(n!) - \ln\left(\sum_{j=1}^r y_{ij}!\right) \right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\sum_{j=2}^r \left(y_{ij} (x_{ij}\beta_j) - \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^r e^{x_{ij}\beta_j}\right) \right) + \ln(n!) - \ln\left(\sum_{j=1}^r y_{ij}!\right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\delta l}{\delta \beta_j} = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_{ij} - p_{ij}(\beta)] x_{ijk} = 0, \quad j = 2, 3, \dots, r. \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p.$$

The information matrix is:

$$I(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i(\beta) (1 - p_i(\beta)) x_i x_i'$$

Here, β is an $(r-1)$ vector of parameters, and each vector consists of $(p+1)$ parameters. The second order derivative of the log-likelihood equation in multinomial logistic regression is given by:

$$\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \beta_j \partial \beta_k} = - \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ijk} x'_{ijk} p_{ij}(\beta) (1 - p_{ij}(\beta))$$

which is the Hessian matrix. The divide and recombine approach can be employed in large datasets with polytomous response variables. An approach described by [Karim et al. \(2019\)](#). The steps of the D&R approach for a generalized linear model with a log link function with a polytomous response are as follows:

1. The entire dataset is divided into s subsets, each with identical structures, where X_s and Y_s are vectors of the design matrix and responses to the subset s .
2. For the s th partitioned subset, compute $\hat{\beta}_s, s = 1, 2, 3, \dots, S$, which is obtained by solving the following equations:

$$\frac{\delta l}{\delta \beta_{sj}} = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_{sij} - p_{sij}(\beta)] x_{sijk} = 0, \quad s = 1, 2, 3, \dots, S, \quad j = 2, 3, \dots, r, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p.$$

3. Recombine separate estimates obtained from step 2 as:

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{\sum_{s=1}^S \hat{\beta}_s}{S}$$

3 Division and recombination procedures

According to [Hafen \(2016\)](#), division in a dataset in the D&R approach can be done through conditioning-variable division or replicate division. The condition variable division uses stratification of data based on one or more variables, while the replicate division uses random sampling without replacement. The replicate division enables simple and faster computations, but there may be a small loss in accuracy compared to the complete data estimate. The divisions from the dataset should be manageable in memory and allow for further breakdown if necessary.

Again, the recombination procedure includes statistical, analytic, and visual recombination ([Guha et al., 2012](#)). The statistical recombination method refers to the recombination of outputs obtained from each subset. Continued analysis of the outputs from each subset is called analytic recombination. Outputs can be handled as small data, then they result in substantial data reduction. In such cases, analyzing these small datasets is an essential component of the D&R Approach. Visual recombination explores detailed data at their most granular level, and subsets that contain fine-grained information are utilized as highlighted by [Guha et al. \(2009\)](#).

3.1 Proposed division method

In working with generalized linear models, our main concern is to choose the proper division method. Therefore, we followed an alternative approach. Suppose that the dataset contains n observations. We wish to divide the dataset into s where $s = 1, 2, \dots, S$ subsets so that each subset can be fitted onto memory. Each subset contains observations $\leq n_s$ such that $\sum_{s=1}^S n_s = n$. The splitting approach follows a sequential order starting from the topmost observation. These procedures are also referred to as the serial partitioning method, as described by ([Rathi et al., 2004](#)). This procedure is different from the previously proposed division procedure for the D&R-based

estimation. We prove that this division procedure and our proposed S.E. estimation scheme provide accurate estimates of the D&R-based estimators for GLMs.

4 Proposed aggregated standard error estimation schemes

Due to the absence of combined standard error and confidence interval estimation for D&R-based estimators for GLMs, this paper aims to address this gap and establish a comprehensive framework. We propose a novel method for estimating the aggregated standard error and confidence intervals. The proposed scheme is characterized by its robustness and broad applicability across different GLMs. The estimation procedure encompassed several key steps that are outlined below:

1. The entire dataset is divided into s subsets.
2. For the sth partitioned subset, compute $\hat{\beta}_s, s = 1, 2, 3, \dots, S$.
3. Compute: $V(\hat{\beta}_s), s = 1, 2, 3, \dots, S$ for each subset.
4. Now, obtain $\frac{V(\hat{\beta}_s)}{S}$, where S denotes the number of subsets.
5. Obtain

$$\begin{aligned} Varinace &= \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{V(\hat{\beta}_s)}{S} \\ &= \frac{1}{S^2} \sum_{s=1}^S V(\hat{\beta}_s) \\ &= \frac{1}{S^2} [V(\hat{\beta}_1) + V(\hat{\beta}_2) + \dots + V(\hat{\beta}_s)] \end{aligned}$$

6. The standard error is obtained as:

$$S.E = \sqrt{\frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{V(\hat{\beta}_s)}{S}}$$

Fig. 1: Proposed aggregated standard error estimation for D&R-based estimators in GLMs

5 Application to a synthetic dataset

This section evaluates the effectiveness of the D&R approach for different GLMs. For the demonstration, we use a publicly available dataset from the UCI Machine Learning Repository, namely Heart Disease [Dataset] (Janosi et al., 1988). Among the four datasets available at the UCI machine learning repository, we select the Cleveland Heart Disease Dataset, which has 14 variables.

Using the synthpop package (Nowok et al., 2016) in R, we created a synthetic dataset via the `syn()` function. We used the processed Cleveland dataset, which contains only 297 rows with 14 variables. Synthpop tries to mimic the original data as much as possible, but the accuracy may vary. The proportion of participants to variables is one factor that influences the data set. Synthetic data maintains variable relationships, so more variables mean the function must account for more scenarios. With the `syn()` function, we set the data generation method to CART, $m=1$, and $k=5000000$. We set m as the number of synthetic datasets and k as the number of rows to generate. We generated the data one at a time and saved it. This dataset is available to download at: [Cleveland Heart Disease Synthetic Dataset](#)

Table 1: Attribute description of the Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Attribute name	Code	Measurement Unit	Type of Variable
Age	Age	In years	Numeric
Sex	Sex	0, 1	Dichotomous
Chest pain type	Chest_Pain_Type	1,2,3,4	Categorical
Resting blood pressure (on admission to the hospital) (in mm Hg)	Resting_Blood_Pressure	mm Hg	Numeric
Serum cholesterol (in mg/dl)	Serum_cholesterol	mg/dl	Numeric
Fasting blood sugar > 120 mg/dl	Fasting_Blood_Sugar	0, 1	Dichotomous
Resting electrocardiographic	Resting_ECG	0, 1, 2	Categorical
Maximum heart rate achieved	Max_Heart_Rate_Achieved	71–202	Numeric
Exercise-induced angina	Exercise_Induced_Angina	0, 1	Dichotomous
ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest	ST_Depression_Exercise	Depression	Numeric
slope: the slope of the peak exercise ST segment	Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment	0,1,2	Categorical
number of major vessels (0-3) colored by flourosopy	Num_Major_Vessles_Flouro	0,1,2,3	Count
A blood disorder called thalassemia	Thalassemia	3, 6, 7	Categorical
Diagnosis of Heart Disease	Diagonosis_Heart_Disease	0, 1	Dichotomous

Source: [Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset](#)

Table 2: Nominal attribute description of the Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Attribute name	Description
Sex	1=male 0=female
Chest pain type	1= typical angina 2= atypical angina 3=nonanginal pain 4=asymptomatic
Fasting blood sugar>120 mg/dl	1 = true 0 = false
Resting electrocardiographic results	0= normal 1= showing ST-T wave abnormality 2= showing definite or probable left ventricular hypertrophy
Exercise-induced angina	1= yes 0 = no
Slope: the slope of the peak exercise ST segment	1=upsloping 2=flat 3=downsloping 3=normal
A blood disorder called thalassemia	6=fixed defect 7=reversable defect
Diagnosis of Heart Disease	1 = heart disease 0 = normal

Source: [Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset](#)

The synthetic dataset is systematically partitioned into ten parts using the sequential partitioning method discussed in section 3.1. Each resulting subset contains 500,000 rows, with the initial subset containing the first 500,000 rows, the second subset including the subsequent 500,000 rows, and so on. The desired model is fitted independently to each subset without any communication between subsets. In fitting linear regression models, the "serum cholesterol" is designated as the response variable, whereas all other variables are treated as the predictors. For fitting the logistic regression model, the variable "diagnosis of heart disease" is treated as the response. The Poisson model utilizes the "number of major vessels colored by fluoroscopy" variable as the response, and the multinomial logistic regression model incorporates the "type of chest pain" as the response variable. The results from each subset are combined via the methods discussed in sections 2.1 to 2.4. Standard errors and confidence intervals are calculated via the method described in section 4. Finally, we construct tables that show a comparison of results obtained through the D&R approach along with the results provided by other R packages, such as stats and speedglm, to verify the accuracy of the estimates.

Table 3: Comparison of the coefficients of the estimates for the linear, logistic, and Poisson models using Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Variables	Estimate								
	Linear regression model			Logistic regression model			Poisson regression model		
	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()
(Intercept)	160.735	160.735	160.735	-5.027	-5.027	-5.027	-3.630	-3.630	-3.630
Age	0.824	0.824	0.824	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.047	0.047	0.047
Sex1	-23.482	-23.482	-23.482	0.154	0.154	0.154	0.214	0.214	0.214
Chest_Pain_Type2	7.227	7.227	7.227	0.218	0.218	0.218	-0.080	-0.080	-0.080
Chest_Pain_Type3	-2.251	-2.251	-2.251	0.204	0.204	0.204	0.147	0.147	0.147
Chest_Pain_Type 4	4.415	4.415	4.415	1.747	1.748	1.748	0.225	0.225	0.225
Resting_Blood_Pressure	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.010	0.010	0.010	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003
Serum_Cholesterol	—	—	—	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fasting_Blood_Sugar1	-3.026	-3.026	-3.026	0.043	0.043	0.043	0.460	0.460	0.460
Resting_ECG1	18.395	18.395	18.395	-0.028	-0.028	-0.028	0.007	0.007	0.007
Resting_ECG2	18.350	18.350	18.350	0.027	0.027	0.027	-0.011	-0.011	-0.011
Max_Heart_Rate_Achieved	0.168	0.168	0.168	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
Exercise_Induced_Anginal	6.375	6.375	6.375	0.039	0.039	0.039	0.028	0.028	0.028
ST_Depression_Exercise	2.904	2.904	2.904	0.207	0.207	0.207	0.180	0.180	0.180
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment2	2.685	2.685	2.685	0.401	0.401	0.401	-0.051	-0.051	-0.051
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment3	0.236	0.236	0.236	-0.071	-0.071	-0.071	-0.043	-0.043	-0.043
Num_Major_Vessels_Flouro	-0.021	-0.021	-0.021	0.725	0.725	0.725	—	—	—
Thalassaemia6	-11.756	-11.756	-11.756	1.947	1.947	1.947	-0.129	-0.129	-0.129
Thalassaemia7	2.058	2.058	2.058	1.751	1.751	1.751	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115
Diagnosis_Heart_Disease1	1.353	1.353	1.353	—	—	—	0.771	0.771	0.771

Table 4: Comparison of standard errors for linear, logistic, and Poisson models using Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Variables	Standard Error								
	Linear regression model			Logistic regression model			Poisson regression model		
	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()
(Intercept)	0.334	0.334	0.334	0.019	0.019	0.019	0.008	0.008	0.008
Age	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sex1	0.052	0.052	0.052	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001
Chest_Pain_Type2	0.099	0.099	0.099	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.003
Chest_Pain_Type3	0.091	0.091	0.091	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.002
Chest_Pain_Type4	0.093	0.093	0.093	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.002
Resting_Blood_Pressure	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Serum_Cholesterol	—	—	—	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fasting_Blood_Sugar1	0.065	0.065	0.065	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.001	0.001	0.001
Resting_ECG1	0.192	0.192	0.192	0.011	0.011	0.011	0.005	0.005	0.005
Resting_ECG2	0.046	0.046	0.046	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001
Max_Heart_Rate_Achieved	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Exercise_Induced_Anginal	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001
ST_Depression_Exercise	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment2	0.054	0.054	0.054	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment3	0.096	0.096	0.096	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.002
Num_Major_Vessels_Flouro	0.026	0.026	0.026	0.001	0.001	0.001	—	—	—
Thalassaemia6	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.002
Thalassaemia7	0.056	0.056	0.056	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001
Diagnosis_Heart_Disease1	0.057	0.057	0.057	—	—	—	0.001	0.001	0.001

Table 5: Comparison of t values and z values for linear, logistic, and Poisson models using Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Variables	t value						z value					
	Linear regression model			Logistic regression model			Logistic regression model			Poisson regression model		
	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()
(Intercept)	481.186	481.193	481.193	-271.467	-271.494	-271.494	-427.110	-427.110	-427.123	-427.110	-427.123	-427.123
Age	281.828	281.832	281.832	58.634	58.637	58.637	642.566	642.566	642.583	642.566	642.583	642.583
Sex 1	-452.615	-452.620	-452.620	52.900	52.902	52.902	138.612	138.612	138.619	138.612	138.619	138.619
Chest_Pain_Type2	72.804	72.805	72.805	40.626	40.638	40.638	-27.539	-27.539	-27.535	-27.539	-27.535	-27.535
Chest_Pain_Type3	-24.715	-24.715	-24.716	42.833	42.846	42.846	61.962	61.962	61.956	61.962	61.956	61.956
Chest_Pain_Type4	47.519	47.520	47.520	366.039	366.093	366.093	96.500	96.500	96.499	96.500	96.499	96.499
Resting_Blood_Pressure	80.943	80.944	80.944	139.919	139.935	139.935	-82.761	-82.761	-82.763	-82.761	-82.763	-82.763
Serum_Cholesterol	—	—	—	16.333	16.336	16.336	35.663	35.663	35.663	35.663	35.663	35.663
Fasting_Blood_Sugar1	-46.749	-46.750	-46.750	12.103	12.102	12.102	346.776	346.776	346.778	346.776	346.778	346.778
Resting_ECG1 -1	95.654	95.664	95.664	-2.626	-2.631	-2.631	1.455	1.455	1.478	1.455	1.478	1.478
Resting_ECG2	402.510	402.512	402.512	10.860	10.860	10.860	-9.941	-9.941	-9.936	-9.941	-9.936	-9.936
Max_Heart_Rate_Achieved	135.464	135.465	135.466	15.128	15.128	15.128	-32.403	-32.403	-32.391	-32.403	-32.391	-32.391
Exercise_Induced_Angina 1	115.704	115.705	115.705	13.301	13.301	13.301	23.309	23.309	23.316	23.309	23.316	23.316
ST_Depression_Exercise	125.208	125.210	125.210	161.523	161.532	161.532	377.397	377.397	377.412	377.397	377.412	377.412
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment2	50.066	50.066	50.066	141.418	141.430	141.430	-38.248	-38.248	-38.249	-38.248	-38.249	-38.249
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment3	2.446	2.446	2.446	-13.655	-13.656	-13.656	-20.130	-20.130	-20.126	-20.130	-20.126	-20.126
Num_Major_Vessels_Flouro	-0.813	-0.813	-0.813	500.713	500.773	500.773	—	—	—	—	—	—
Thalassaemia6	-118.147	-118.150	-118.150	365.542	365.598	365.598	-60.752	-60.752	-60.748	-60.752	-60.748	-60.748
Thalassaemia 7	36.908	36.908	36.908	648.015	648.086	648.086	-87.304	-87.304	-87.317	-87.304	-87.317	-87.317
Diagnosis_Heart_Disease1	23.665	23.665	23.665	—	—	—	534.456	534.456	534.462	534.456	534.462	534.462

Table 6: Comparison of P values for linear, logistic, and Poisson models using Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Variables	Pr ($> t $)				Pr ($> z $)				
	Linear regression model		Logistic regression model		Logistic regression model		Poisson regression model		
	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()
(Intercept)	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Age	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Sex1	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Chest_Pain_Type2	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Chest_Pain_Type3	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Chest_Pain_Type4	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Resting_Blood_Pressure	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Serum_Cholesterol	—	—	—	—	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Fasting_Blood_Sugar1	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Resting_ECG1	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.009	< 2e-16	0.009	0.142	< 2e-16	0.000
Resting_ECG2	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.139
Max_Heart_Rate_Achieved	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Exercise_Induced_Anginal	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
ST_Depression_Exercise	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment2	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment3	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Num_Major_Vessels_Flouro	0.416	0.416	0.416	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Thalassaemia6	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
halassaemia7	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000
Diagnosis_Heart_Disease1	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000	—	—	—	0.000	< 2e-16	0.000

Table 7: Comparison of confidence intervals for linear, logistic, and Poisson models using Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Variables	Confidence Interval								
	Linear regression model			Logistic regression model			Poisson regression model		
	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()	Using D&R	Using glm()	Using speedglm()
(Intercept)	[160.08, 161.39]	[160.08, 161.39]	[160.08, 161.39]	[-5.06,-4.99]	[-5.06, -4.99]	[-5.06,-4.99]	[-3.65, -3.61]	[-3.65, -3.61]	[-3.65, -3.61]
Age	[0.82,0.83]	[0.82,0.83]	[0.82,0.83]	[0.01,0.01]	[0.01,0.01]	[0.01,0.01]	[0.05,0.05]	[0.05,0.05]	[0.05,0.05]
Sex1	[-23.58,-23.38]	[-23.58, -23.38]	[-23.58,-23.38]	[0.15, 0.16]	[0.15, 0.16]	[0.15, 0.16]	[0.21,0.22]	[0.21,0.22]	[0.21,0.22]
Chest_Pain_Type2	[7.03, 7.42]	[7.03, 7.42]	[7.03, 7.42]	[0.21,0.23]	[0.21, 0.23]	[0.21,0.23]	[-0.09,-0.07]	[-0.09,-0.07]	[-0.09,-0.07]
Chest_Pain_Type3	[-2.43, -2.07]	[-2.43,-2.07]	[-2.43, -2.07]	[0.19, 0.21]	[0.19, 0.21]	[0.19, 0.21]	[0.14,0.15]	[0.14,0.15]	[0.14,0.15]
Chest_Pain_Type 4	[4.23,4.6]	[4.23,4.6]	[4.23,4.6]	[1.74, 1.76]	[1.74, 1.76]	[1.74, 1.76]	[0.22,0.23]	[0.22,0.23]	[0.22,0.23]
Resting_Blood_Pressure	[0.11, 0.11]	[0.11, 0.11]	[0.11, 0.11]	[0.01, 0.01]	[0.01, 0.01]	[0.01, 0.01]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]
Serum_Cholesterol	—	—	—	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]
Fasting_Blood_Sugar 1	[-3.15,-2.9]	[-3.15, -2.9]	[-3.15,-2.9]	[0.04, 0.05]	[0.04, 0.05]	[0.04, 0.05]	[0.46,0.46]	[0.46,0.46]	[0.46,0.46]
Resting_ECG1	[18.02, 18.77]	[18.02, 18.77]	[18.02, 18.77]	[-0.05,-0.01]	[-0.05, -0.01]	[-0.05, -0.01]	[0,0.02]	[0,0.02]	[0,0.02]
Resting_ECG2	[18.26, 18.44]	[18.26, 18.44]	[18.26, 18.44]	[0.02,0.03]	[0.02, 0.03]	[0.02,0.03]	[-0.01,-0.01]	[-0.01,-0.01]	[-0.01,-0.01]
Max_Heart_Rate_Achieved	[0.17, 0.17]	[0.17, 0.17]	[0.17, 0.17]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]	[0,0]
Exercise_Induced_Anginal	[6.27,6.48]	[6.27,6.48]	[6.27,6.48]	[0.03, 0.04]	[0.03, 0.04]	[0.03, 0.04]	[0.03,0.03]	[0.03,0.03]	[0.03,0.03]
ST_Depression_Exercise	[2.86, 2.95]	[2.86, 2.95]	[2.86, 2.95]	[0.2,0.21]	[0.2, 0.21]	[0.2, 0.21]	[0.18,0.18]	[0.18,0.18]	[0.18,0.18]
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment2	[2.58, 2.79]	[2.58, 2.79]	[2.58, 2.79]	[0.4, 0.41]	[0.4, 0.41]	[0.4, 0.41]	[-0.05,-0.05]	[-0.05,-0.05]	[-0.05, -0.05]
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment 3	[0.05, 0.42]	[0.05, 0.42]	[0.05, 0.42]	[-0.08, -0.06]	[-0.08, -0.06]	[-0.08,-0.06]	[-0.05,-0.04]	[-0.05,-0.04]	[-0.05, -0.04]
Num_Major_Vessels_Flouro	[-0.07, 0.03]	[-0.07, 0.03]	[-0.07, 0.03]	[0.72,0.73]	[0.73,0.73]	[0.72, 0.73]	—	—	—
Thalassemia6	[-11.95,-11.56]	[-11.95,-11.56]	[-11.95,-11.56]	[1.94, 1.96]	[1.94, 1.96]	[1.94, 1.96]	[-0.13,-0.12]	[-0.13,-0.12]	[-0.13, -0.12]
Thalassemia7	[1.95, 2.17]	[1.95, 2.17]	[1.95, 2.17]	[1.75, 1.76]	[1.75, 1.76]	[1.75, 1.76]	[-0.12,-0.11]	[-0.12, -0.11]	[-0.12, -0.11]
Diagnosis_Heart_Disease1	[1.24, 1.47]	[1.24, 1.47]	[1.24, 1.47]	—	—	—	[0.77,0.77]	[0.77,0.77]	[0.77,0.77]

Table 8: Comparison of the Coefficients of the Estimate and Standard Errors for the multinomial logistic regression models using Cleveland heart disease synthetic dataset

Variables	Estimate								Standard Error							
	Estimate 2		Estimate 3		Estimate 4		Standard Error 2		Standard Error 3		Standard Error 4					
	Using D&R	Using multinom()	Using D&R	Using multinom()	Using D&R	Using multinom()	Using D&R	Using multinom()	Using D&R	Using multinom()	Using D&R	Using multinom()				
(Intercept)	7.865	7.865	10.760	10.759	12.482	12.482	0.034	0.034	0.031	0.031	0.032	0.032				
Age	-0.030	-0.030	-0.027	-0.027	-0.044	-0.044	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000				
Sex1	-0.798	-0.798	-1.254	-1.254	-1.265	-1.265	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005				
Resting_Blood_Pressure	-0.021	-0.021	-0.027	-0.027	-0.023	-0.023	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000				
Serum_Cholesterol	0.002	0.002	-0.002	-0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000				
Fasting_Blood_Sugar1	-0.835	-0.835	-0.050	-0.050	-1.016	-1.016	0.006	0.006	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005				
Resting_ECG1	0.117	0.116	-0.061	-0.062	0.012	0.011	0.019	0.019	0.018	0.018	0.019	0.019				
Resting_ECG2	-0.838	-0.838	-0.483	-0.483	-0.133	-0.133	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004				
Max_Heart_Rate_Achieved	-0.008	-0.008	-0.016	-0.016	-0.034	-0.034	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000				
Exercise_Induced_Anginal	0.095	0.095	0.343	0.343	1.862	1.862	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006				
ST_Depression_Exercise	-0.872	-0.872	-0.172	-0.172	-0.365	-0.365	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002				
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment2	-0.493	-0.493	-0.422	-0.422	-0.633	-0.632	0.005	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.005				
Peak_Exercise_ST_Segment3	-0.565	-0.565	-0.457	-0.457	-0.545	-0.545	0.009	0.009	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.008				
Num_Major_Vessels_Ftouro	-0.042	-0.042	0.123	0.123	0.212	0.212	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002				
Thalassemia6	0.203	0.203	0.209	0.209	0.344	0.344	0.011	0.011	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009				
Thalassemia7	-0.034	-0.035	-0.044	-0.044	0.385	0.385	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005				
Diagnosis_Heart_Disease1	0.105	0.105	0.153	0.153	1.675	1.675	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005				

The coefficient of estimates of linear, logistic, Poisson, and multinomial logistic regression, obtained via D&R, `glm()`, and `speedglm()`, is presented in Table 3. The estimates obtained using the D&R method align precisely with those obtained from `glm()` and `speedglm()` functions in R. Table 4 presents the standard errors for different models obtained via the method discussed in section 4. The standard deviations obtained through D&R mirror those produced by `glm()` and `speedglm()`. Table 5,6,7 presents the t and z values, probability values, and confidence intervals for different GLMs under consideration. D&R exhibits exact and identical results with those obtained from `glm()` and `speedglm()`. Furthermore, Table 8 illustrates the coefficients of estimates and standard errors for multinomial logistic regression models employing both D&R and `multinom()` from the `nnet` package in R and no significant mismatch is seen among results. We can infer that the D&R methods discussed in the preceding sections, in conjunction with the division approach and the proposed standard error estimation techniques, produce accurate estimates as `glm()` and `speedglm()` functions. A noticeable reduction in object and reduced computation time is seen upon fitting the models in the D&R strategy. This verifies the efficiency of the D&R method for fitting GLMs in large datasets, particularly in terms of computational time and memory efficiency.

6 Conclusion

This paper presents an extensive overview of various divide and recombine (D&R) techniques for different GLMs to large-scale datasets. The preliminary section focuses on different divide and recombine approaches with their operational principles for linear regression models. We detail the D&R framework with respect to logistic, Poisson, and multinomial logistic regression models. The next part of the paper elaborates on current division strategies; then we introduce a new division strategy called sequential partitioning for D&R-based estimators for GLMs. We also present a novel method to derive the standard errors and confidence intervals for D&R-based estimators, which enable inference on variable estimates within various models. We then created a synthetic dataset of 5M observations and 14 variables to evaluate the performance of D&R methods. Using this dataset, we estimated linear, logistic, Poisson, and multinomial logistic regression models using the D&R approach. The resulting outcomes were benchmarked against the results from `glm()` and `speedglm()` in R, showing no significant differences. This provides confirmation of methodological correctness as well as correct implementation of D&R methods in GLMs for large data sets.

References

- Bühlmann, P., Drineas, P., Kane, M., Laan, M.: Handbook of Big Data. CRC Press, ??? (2016)
- Cleveland, W.S., Hafen, R.: Divide and recombine (d&r): Data science for large complex data. *Statistical Analysis & Data Mining* **7**(6) (2014)

- Guha, S., Hafen, R., Rounds, J., Xia, J., Li, J., Xi, B., Cleveland, W.S.: Large complex data: divide and recombine (d&r) with rhipe. *Stat* **1**(1), 53–67 (2012)
- Guha, S., Kidwell, P., Hafen, R.P., Cleveland, W.S.: Visualization databases for the analysis of large complex datasets. In: *Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pp. 193–200 (2009). PMLR
- Hafen, R.: *Divide and Recombine: Approach for Detailed Analysis and Visualization of Large Complex Data*. (2016)
- Janosi, A., Steinbrunn, W., Pfisterer, M., Detrano, R.: Uci machine learning repository-heart disease data set. School Inf. Comput. Sci., Univ. California, Irvine, CA, USA (1988)
- Karim, M.R., Islam, M.A., *et al.*: *Reliability and Survival Analysis*. Springer, ??? (2019)
- Lee, J.Y., Brown, J.J., Ryan, L.M.: Sufficiency revisited: rethinking statistical algorithms in the big data era. *The American Statistician* **71**(3), 202–208 (2017)
- Nowok, B., Raab, G.M., Dibben, C.: synthpop: Bespoke creation of synthetic data in r. *Journal of statistical software* **74**, 1–26 (2016)
- Nelder, J.A., Wedderburn, R.W.: Generalized linear models. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series A: Statistics in Society* **135**(3), 370–384 (1972)
- Rathi, R., Cook, D.J., Holder, L.B.: Serial partitioning approach to scaling graph-based knowledge discovery. PhD thesis, University of Texas at Arlington (2004)
- Xi, R., Lin, N., Chen, Y.: Compression and aggregation for logistic regression analysis in data cubes. *IEEE transactions on knowledge and data engineering* **21**(4), 479–492 (2008)